

DIVERSify-ing for sustainability using cereal-legume 'plant teams'

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Summary

Increasing the diversity of crop systems could enhance and stabilise crop yields while increasing sustainability. We report preliminary findings from two trials at the James Hutton Institute, UK, aiming to optimise the performance of spring cereal-legume species mixtures or 'plant teams'. Commercial cereal and legume cultivars were tested for their performance in plant teams (compared to monocultures) under conventional and reduced input management. Wheat-faba bean plant teams were grown for silage and barley-pea plant teams were grown for grain. Over-yielding of species mixtures was detected in both trials. The best performing wheat-faba bean combinations contained the wheat variety Tybalt, while those based on the pea varieties Ingrid and Daytona combined with barley cultivars RGT Planet or KWS Sassy performed best in barley-pea plant teams. Preliminary analysis of plant traits is used to identify the mechanisms promoting productivity in these plant teams.

Key words: Barley, diversification, faba bean, intercropping, pea, wheat

Introduction

Crop diversification is a key component of UK and EU strategies for enhancing agricultural sustainability and to ensure secure production of agricultural commodities. Diversifying crop systems is one approach for maximising agricultural productivity, efficiency and sustainability. Options for diversification include diversified crop rotations (temporal diversification), targeted habitat management, and intercropping (spatial diversification); here, we focus on intercropping, i.e. simultaneously growing more than one crop species at a given location (Vandermeer, 1989). Increased plant diversity promotes ecological functions central to crop production, but intensive crop systems are currently species-poor. Diversity and productivity can be enhanced by intercropping, but the benefits associated with this cropping strategy could be improved by understanding the plant traits and biological mechanisms that underpin the capacity of some crop species mixtures to 'over yield' (i.e. produce more yield per unit area than expected based on a weighted average of the monoculture yields of the component species; Loreau, 1998; Hector *et al.*, 2002), particularly under reduced agrochemical inputs.

Species-rich systems often show higher productivity than monocultures, explained by selection and complementarity effects (Hector *et al.*, 2010) that enhance plant resource capture. Moreover, compared to monocultures, diverse vegetation often shows reduced pest and disease severity (Scherber *et al.*, 2010), and greater resilience to stress and environmental fluctuations. Greater heterogeneity in crop vegetation could, therefore, increase and stabilise yields and enhance resource-use efficiency (Brooker *et al.*, 2015). Ecological principles that are used to understand processes promoting productivity in natural plant communities and diversity experiments can be used to identify the plant traits and mechanisms that promote productivity in crop species mixtures (Ren *et al.*, 2014; Brooker *et al.*, 2015) or ‘plant teams’. The EU-funded Horizon2020 project DIVERSify (www.plant-teams.eu) adopts a multi-disciplinary approach to test these concepts and develop methods and tools for crop improvement in plant teams. Legume supported intercrops are often exploited to achieve ‘over yielding’, under conditions of low-input (Iannetta *et al.*, 2016). In the first year (2017), field trials of cereal-legume mixtures were established at research and stakeholder sites in a range of pedo-climatic zones across Europe. We report preliminary results from two trials conducted at the James Hutton Institute, UK, conducted under conventional and low nitrogen fertiliser inputs, to identify the best-performing commercial varieties in cereal-legume plant teams.

Materials and Methods

Two field trials were established between 29–30 March 2017 at the Balruddery Farm site (longitude $-3^{\circ}11'56.33''\text{E}$, latitude $56^{\circ}48'16.97''\text{N}$) of the James Hutton Institute, Dundee, UK. Commercial cultivars of cereal crops (spring wheat and spring barley) and legume crops (spring faba bean and spring pea) were selected from national recommended lists. Trials were laid out as a randomised split-block design with three (wheat-faba bean) or four (barley-pea) replicate blocks; nitrogen (N) treatment whole-plots (comprising 25% standard-N addition and zero-N addition) were randomised within blocks, and variety plots (cultivar monocultures and mixtures of each cereal and legume cultivar) were randomised within whole-plots. Plant treatments were assigned at random to plots within each half-block. Seeds were sown at monoculture densities of 360 seed m^{-2} for barley, 440 seed m^{-2} for wheat, 80 seed m^{-2} for peas and 50 seed m^{-2} for beans, into a stale seed bed treated with a pre-emergence herbicide. Sowing densities of each crop in the species mixtures treatments were half those of monoculture plots. Plot size was 100 m \times 1.55 m for the wheat-faba bean trial, which was destined for silage production, and 1.55 m \times 6 m in paired beds for the barley-pea trial. Fleece was laid to cover the pea-barley trial from after sowing until barley plants were tillering but before stem elongation (approximate GS30: Zadocks *et al.*, 1974). Fertiliser was applied just after sowing. No other chemicals were applied during the trial period with the exception of desiccant applied to the barley-pea trial approximately 10 days prior to harvest. The wheat-faba bean trial was cut and baled on 2 August 2017 and the pea-barley trial was combined-harvested on 28–30 August 2017.

Plot-scale and individual-based measurements of plant traits (e.g. emergence, development, tillering), agronomic performance (e.g. lodging, biomass and grain yield) and environmental parameters (e.g. pest and disease incidence) were collected throughout the growing season, along with post-harvest analysis of crop yield and quality, following standard protocols developed in the project (Kiær *et al.*, unpublished). Traits that were time-intensive to measure could only be conducted on two or three replicate plots. Over yielding was estimated as the percentage deviation of average yields of mixture plots from the expected yield calculated from average yields of monoculture plots of each component using the formula:

$$E_i = p_i M_i$$

where p_i is the proportion of species i in the mixture (i.e. 0.5, as sowing density was 50% that of monocultures), M_i is the yield of species i in monoculture and E_i is its expected yield based on the

yield in monoculture (Loreau, 1998). Statistical analysis was conducted using analysis of variance for split-plot designs, with block, whole-plot (nested within block) and plot (nested within whole-plot) assigned as random effects. Data were inspected for normality of distribution and limited heteroscedasticity. The effects of the main factors N-addition and cultivar(s) were tested and their two-way interaction. All analyses were conducted using Genstat (18th edition, VSN International, UK).

Results

Spring wheat-faba bean

Fresh mass of plot bales (per 155 m²) of spring wheat-faba bean mixtures were highest for faba bean monocultures and lowest for wheat monocultures (data not shown). Wheat-faba bean mixtures gave intermediate values for bale mass that were, on average, higher than predicted from monoculture values, particularly for mixtures including Tybalt, which performed better than Alderon in monocultures and in mixtures (Table 1). In faba bean, cultivar treatment had a significant effect on the number of bean pods per plant ($F_{5,20}=3.33$, $P=0.024$) and seeds per plant ($F_{5,20}=2.85$, $P=0.042$). Highest values were detected for Boxer in monocultures and mixtures, and lowest values were detected for Fuego in monoculture (Fig. 1A). For wheat, there was no significant variation between cultivar treatments in tiller or ear number per plant (data not shown). For all the tested variables in both crop types, there were no significant effects of N treatment nor interaction between N treatment and cultivar.

Table 1. *Percentage deviation of average yields of wheat faba-bean mixture plots from the expected yield calculated from average yields of monoculture plots of each component. See text for definition of expected yield. Positive values indicate a higher yield in mixtures than would be predicted from yields obtained in monoculture*

Faba bean–wheat mixture	% change in mass
Boxer & Alderon	6.0
Boxer & Tybalt	23.2
Fuego & Alderon	3.4
Fuego & Tybalt	19.2

Spring barley-pea

Total seed mass per plot (9.3 m²) was highest for barley monocrops and lowest for pea monocrops (data not shown). Barley-pea mixtures gave intermediate values for total grain mass that were higher than predicted from monocrop values, with the exception of three combinations (Table 2). Best-performing mixtures included pea varieties Ingrid and Daytona combined with RGT Planet or KWS Sassy (Table 2). Worst-performing mixtures included pea varieties Clara and Sakura combined with Tamtam or Laureate (Table 2). In pea, cultivar treatment had a significant effect on the number of pea pods per plant ($F_{19,76}=3.26$, $P<0.001$; three replicate plots) and seeds per plant ($F_{19,38}=2.34$, $P=0.012$; two replicate plots). Numbers of pea pods per plant and seeds per plant were highest in monocultures, with lowest values in mixtures containing Clara and highest values in mixtures with Sakura (Fig. 1B).

Barley cultivars showed no significant variation between treatments or genotypes in tiller or ear number per plant (data not shown). For all the tested variables, there were no significant effects of N treatment nor interaction between N treatment and cultivar.

Fig. 1 Numbers of pods (filled bars) and seeds (grey bars) per plant for five representative plants harvested from plots of (A) spring faba bean grown in monoculture or mixture with spring wheat and (B) spring pea grown in monoculture or mixture with spring barley. Vertical lines represent the least significant difference between values for different levels of the cultivar treatment.

Table 2. Percentage deviation of average yields of pea-barley mixture plots from the expected yield calculated from average yields of monoculture plots of each component. See text for definition of expected yield. Positive values indicate a higher yield in mixtures than would be predicted from yields obtained in monoculture, while negative values represent a lower yield

Pea-barley mixture	% change in mass
Clara & KWS Sassy	7.1
Clara & Laureate	5.1
Clara & RGT Planet	16.7
Clara & Tamtam	-5.7
Daytona & KWS Sassy	22.8
Daytona & Laureate	16.0
Daytona & RGT Planet	23.8
Daytona & Tamtam	16.0
Ingrid & KWS Sassy	22.7
Ingrid & Laureate	22.4
Ingrid & RGT Planet	29.0
Ingrid & Tamtam	19.7
Sakura & KWS Sassy	10.1
Sakura & Laureate	-2.5
Sakura & RGT Planet	11.0
Sakura & Tamtam	-3.9

Discussion

Over-yielding was detected in both sets of species mixtures, following the general pattern for cereal-legume mixtures (Yu *et al.*, 2016). Greater biomass than expected was observed for all spring wheat-faba bean combinations, indicating the potential benefits of plant team cropping for silage production. Although the crops were not grown for grain harvesting, analysis of samples collected from maturing plants gave an indication of one characteristic of the intercrop that might have contributed to the success of the best-performing wheat-bean combinations, which were those including the spring wheat cultivar Tybalt. In the presence of Tybalt, faba bean pod and seed production per plant was maintained at similar values to those observed in faba bean monocultures, suggesting that faba bean plant growth is optimal with this wheat cultivar.

Higher yields than expected were also detected in the majority of spring pea-barley combinations. Plant team grain production was highest for Ingrid and Daytona combined with RGT Planet or KWS Sassy. However, the performance of pea-barley mixtures did not relate directly to individual plant performance in terms of barley tillering and ear production, nor pea pod and seed production. These findings suggest that for pea-barley mixtures, over-yielding of plant teams was explained by different mechanisms from those driving faba bean-wheat over-yielding; these might include increased seedling emergence and higher plant densities.

Further analysis of crop and trait data will be used to identify the mechanisms that promote productivity in plant teams (Brooker *et al.*, 2015) and contribute to increased resource uptake, yield and grain quality in cereal-legume intercrops (Bedoussac *et al.*, 2015). The findings will be used to select the best performing plant teams for further testing in plot-scale trials and large-scale field validation. Using this approach, the project aims to identify complementary legume and cereal crop traits as breeding targets for optimising plant team partners, and to advise farmers on cultivar selection for plant team cropping.

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